

The Role of Women in Sustainability Reporting

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Abstract

The primary focus of this study is to identify the decisive roles played by women in corporate sustainability reporting in Nigeria. The identified independent variables of the study are female CEO, female directors, female membership of audit committee, nomination committee, remuneration committee, and risk committee. Sustainability reporting is the dependent variable, measured by dummy. Secondary data was collected through content analysis from the annual reports and accounts of 134 listed firms from the Main Board of the Nigerian Exchange, for 15 years (2008-2022). Five (5) hypotheses were developed and tested through multiple linear regression and the correlation coefficients analysis was used to identify the relationship between the dependent variable (sustainability reporting) and independent variables (women directors). The findings of the study show that FCEO, female member of remuneration committee, listing age and firm size are statistically significant, whereas female member of audit committee, female directors, female member of risk committee have statistically insignificant impacts. The study is limited by the sample size. It is expected that further research can increase the total sample of companies. Also, future research may add to the study period. Our results show that the R^2 is 45.58%. Further research is expected to add other characteristic variables that may influence the decisions made in a firm. Also, limitations of the study may be in terms of data and methodology and possible omission of some variables.

Keywords: *FCEO, Female Audit Committee Member, Female Directors, Female Nomination Committee Member, Female Remuneration Committee Member, Female Risk Committee Member, Nigeria, Sustainability Reporting*

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1 Introduction

There is a growing interest in the subject of sustainability reporting (SR), also known as sustainability disclosure (SD). For example, several scholars have written on the subject, both at home and away (Abdulwahab et al., 2023; Alsaahli & Malagueño, 2022; Al-Shaer, 2020; Dilling, 2010; Manetti & Becatti, 2009; Manetti, 2011; Masud et al., 2018; Nguyen, 2020; Ong & Djajadikerta, 2020; Reddy & Gordon, 2010; Shamil et al., 2014; Tijjani & Yahaya, 2023; Umar et al., 2021; Usman & Yahaya, 2023; Yahaya & Alkasim, 2021; Yahaya & et al., 2022). There is also a general agreement that the level of SR in Nigeria is low, because most companies concentrate on financial performance reporting, little is done in the area of non-financial performance, which SR addresses.

SR or SD is a system of disclosure of non-financial performance, such as environmental performance (Greenhouse gases, GHG emissions, energy use and efficiency, air pollutants, water use, waste management, and use of eco systems), social performance (workforce health and safety, customer health and safety, diversity and equal opportunity, poverty and community impact, supply chain management, training and education, and customer privacy) and governance performance (code of conduct, business principles, accountability, transparency, disclosure, executive pay, board diversity, board structure, bribery, corruption, stakeholders' engagement, and shareholders' rights).

Despite the interest in SR in Nigeria, there are few empirical studies that examine the factors that determine SR. While we accept that SR is determined by several factors, this study is a novel attempt to examine the role of women directors in encouraging SR. This is the general crush of this paper, and specifically, the paper examines the role of (1) women directors in SR, (2) female CEO in SR, (3) female audit committee member in SR, (4) female remuneration committee member in SR, and (5) female risk committee member in SR, in enhancing SR, among the 134 listed firms in Nigerian Exchange Main Board.

This study's findings may serve policymakers, regulators, investors, market participants, lenders, communities, suppliers, employees, managers, and academic researchers to get valuable guidance from relevant literature. The 134 listed firms on the Main Board of the Nigerian Exchange may improve SR by implementing the regulatory framework introduced and explained in this paper, for effective implementation of SR. The findings may alleviate principal-agent conflicts by ensuring the inclusion of women directors and increasing the number of female directors according

to the Nigerian Code of Corporate Governance of 2018. Furthermore, performance improvement of the listed firms under consideration would gain tremendously, since SR is seen by stakeholders as showing that the firms are responsible corporate citizens, and therefore, view such disclosure favourably. In addition, policy would improve, since the fundamental information required for such policies improvements are provided. Regulators such as the Central Bank of Nigeria, Financial Reporting Council of Nigeria, Nigerian Securities and Exchange Commission, and the Nigerian Exchange would benefit from the findings of this study.

Also, this study, though, novel, it contributes to the body of knowledge on board gender diversity and sustainability reporting, specifically, within an emerging economy, like Nigeria, in which institutions are weak. It also provides foundation for future research; for example, future researchers may decide to increase the number of firms as sample or add to the period of coverage. In addition, future research may adopt a new methodology, entirely different from the methods used in this study.

In terms of scope, the findings of this study are limited to the 134 listed firms on the Main Board of the Nigerian Exchange, for the period of coverage (2008-2022) and the variables considered in this paper. In addition, the scope is limited to the data and methodology used in this paper. The remaining sections of this paper cover literature review, data and methodology, results and discussions, and conclusions and recommendations.

2 Literature Review

This section is titled, literature review; it covers theoretical framework, conceptual literature and empirical literature. Agency theory is used in this paper, in order to resolve the conflict of interest between the principal and agent in a firm. In this case, between the shareholders or lenders and managers. Inclusion of women directors on the board of directors of a firm is part of the larger corporate governance mechanisms.

It is enunciated by both the Central Bank of Nigeria Codes of Corporate Governance for banks (2019, 30 percent) and the Nigerian Corporate Governance Code (2018) issued by the Financial Reporting Council of Nigeria (though no specific percentage, but urged firms to ensure women are represented) on corporate boards. Agency theory explores the association between two or more cooperative players, called principals and agents, in which tasks are mutually delegated. It comes in to ensure that agents (managers) understand their roles in a firm, are directed towards

maximization of the wealth of shareholders. This is, therefore, the basis for bringing in women directors with the hope that they could ensure greater SR, since greater SR may lead to higher financial performance, which has the capacity to increase shareholders' wealth. Thus, the analytical framework, illustrated in this paper is governed by this position. It is also true that the remaining parts of this paper are guided by this analytical framework. Figure 1 illustrates the analytical framework, used in the study.

Figure 1. *Analytical Framework*

Source: The Authors (2023)

Sustainability reported is defined as dummy where "1" is assigned to firm with annual reports with sustainability reports and "0" for otherwise. Similarly, female CEO is defined as dummy where "1" is assigned to companies that have Female CEOs and "0" for otherwise. Female director is defined as the number of female directors divided by total board size (%). Female audit committee member is defined as the number of female audit committee members divided by audit committee members size (%). In the same vein, female remuneration committee member is defined measured as the number of female remuneration committee members divided by remuneration committee members' size (%). Furthermore, measured as the number of female risk committee members divided by risk committee members' size (%). On control variables, leverage is defined as total

liabilities divided by total asset. Firm listing age is defined as number of years a company is trading in the stock exchange. Firm size is defined as natural log of total asset. Finally, firm growth is defined as current year revenue minus previous year revenue divided by previous revenue (%).

In terms of empirical studies, Shamil et al. (2014) investigate the influence of board characteristics on sustainability reporting of listed companies in the Colombo Stock Exchange, Sri Lanka. Results show that boards with female directors are negatively associated with sustainability reporting. This study also found that sustainability reporting is likely to be influenced by firm size and firm growth. Additionally, the study reveals that younger firms are likely to adopt sustainability reporting. Also, Al-Shaer and Zaman (2016) examine the effect of board gender diversity, measured using a range of proxies, on sustainability reporting quality. They find that gender diverse boards are associated with higher quality sustainability reports and independent female directors have greater effect on sustainability reporting quality than female directors.

Ong and Djajadikerta (2018) evaluate the impact of corporate governance on sustainability reporting by investigating companies operating in the Australian resources industry. Significant positive correlation was found between the extent of sustainability disclosures and female directors on the board. Furthermore, Masud et al. (2018) examine the effect of corporate governance on environmental sustainability reporting performance in Bangladesh, India, and Pakistan, using 88 listed organizations' sustainability reports during the years 2009–2016 from the Global Reporting Initiative database. Their results reveal no association between environmental sustainability reporting performance and female directorship. Garcia-Sanchez et al. (2018) examine the relationship between board diversity, in terms of gender differences, and the quality of sustainability reporting, using a sample of 273 firm-year observations from 2006 to 2014. Their evidence is consistent with the presence of women in supervisory and senior management positions, that is, boards with greater female representation increases sustainability disclosure. Female directors are positively associated with more balanced, comparable and reliable sustainability reports. Anazonwu et al. (2018) examine the influence of corporate board diversity on sustainability reporting on a sample of quoted manufacturing firms in Nigeria. The results show that the proportion of women directors' directorships was significant. Naseer and Rashid (2018) empirically scrutinize the relationship between corporate governance and sustainability reporting of 50 non-financial listed firms in Pakistan, for the years 2014-2015. The results reveal that the proportion of female directors on board is not significant with sustainability reporting.

Nguyen (2020) investigate the relationship between board of directors and GRI adherence in sustainability disclosures. The research uses Tobit regression for 388 observations from 97 German listed firms in the period from 2013 to 2016. The results reveal positive impact of board committees on GRI adherence of sustainability reporting in sensitive industry. Chebbia et al. (2020) investigate whether a gender diverse board is associated with environmental sustainability reporting. Using a sample of 833 French firms-year observations over the period 2010-2019, they show that the presence and percentage of women on the board of directors are positively associated with environmental sustainability disclosures.

Pasko et al. (2021) investigate the relationship between corporate governance attributes and sustainability reporting conduct in China on a sample of 10,330 firm-year observations of Chinese listed companies over the period from 2015 to 2018. Results indicate that female directors do not have a significant effect on sustainability reporting conduct in the Chinese institutional settings. Hasan et al. (2021) investigate the determinants of corporate sustainability reporting decision. They use a logistic regression model to analyse data collected from a sample of 138 firms listed on the Pakistan Stock Exchange for the years 2009–2018. They find that firms with more gender-diverse boards are more likely to issue sustainability reports.

Oware et al. (2022) examine the effect of gender board characteristics on the choice of sustainability report format in India. The authors find that female chief executive officers (CEOs) are more likely to choose sustainability reporting. Furthermore, the study shows that gender board diversity (percentage of women over total board size) and females of two or less are insignificant. However, three or more females on the board significantly and positively affect sustainability reporting. Githaiga and Kosgei (2022) investigate the influence of board characteristics on sustainability reporting among listed firms in East Africa. The results reveal that board gender diversity is positively and significantly associated with sustainability reporting.

Based on the foregoing empirical literature, the following hypotheses are developed and tested:

- H₁: FCEO has no significant effect on SR.
- H₂: FACM has no significant effect on SR.
- H₃: FD has no significant effect on SR.
- H₄: FRCM has no significant effect on SR.
- H₅: FRICM has no significant effect on SR.

The remaining parts of this study focus on methodology, results and discussions, and conclusions and recommendations.

3 Methodology

The research design is *ex post facto*, and the population is 156, from which 134 were selected for the study, meaning that 22 listed firms were excluded from the sample. The method used is the multiple regression analysis with the Generalized Methods of Moment (GMM) estimator. The estimated model is given in Equation 1.

$$SR_{i,t} = \alpha + \beta_1 FCEO_{i,t} + \beta_2 FACM_{i,t} + \beta_3 FD_{i,t} + \beta_4 FRCM_{i,t} + \beta_5 FRICM_{i,t} + \beta_6 LEV_{i,t} + \beta_7 LAGE_{i,t} + \beta_8 FS_{i,t} + \beta_9 FG_{i,t} + \epsilon_{i,t}$$

Whereas:

SR is Sustainability Reporting

FCEO is Female CEO

FACM is Female Audit Committee Member

FD is Female Director

FRCM is Female Remuneration Committee Member

FRICM is Female Risk Committee Member

LEV is Leverage

LAGE is Firm Listing Age

FS is Firm Size

FG is Firm Growth

α is Intercept or Constant

β_{1-10} is Beta Coefficients

i is Firm Script (in this study, $i = 134$)

t is Time Script (in this study, $t = 15$ years)

ϵ is Idiosyncratic Error Term

These variables are operationalized in Table 1 as follows.

Table 1. *Variables and their Measurements*

Serial	Variables	Measurements	A priori expectation
1	Y, SR	Measured as dummy where "1" is assigned to firm with annual reports with sustainability reports and "0" for otherwise.	
2	X ₁ , FCEO	Measured as dummy where "1" is assigned to companies that have Female CEOs and "0" for otherwise.	+
3	X ₂ , FACM	Measured as the number of female audit committee members divided by audit committee members' size (%).	+
4	X ₃ , FD	Measured as the number of female directors divided by total board size (%).	+
5	X ₅ , FRCM	Measured as the number of female remuneration committee members divided by remuneration committee members' size (%).	+
6	X ₆ , FRICM	Measured as the number of female risk committee members divided by risk committee members' size (%).	+
7	X ₇ , LEV	Measured as total liabilities divided by total asset.	+/-
8	X ₈ , LAGE	Measured as number of years a company is trading in the stock exchange.	+/-
9	X ₉ , FS	Measured as natural log of total asset.	+/-
10	X ₁₀ , FG	Measured as current year revenue minus previous year revenue divided by previous revenue (%).	+/-

Source: The Authors (2023)

Our a priori expectations based on the independent variables and control variables and their measurements are as follows:

X₁>0, an engagement of FCEO will lead to a rise in sustainability reporting.

X₂>0, a rise in female directors will lead to a rise in sustainability reporting.

X₃>0, a rise in female membership of audit committee will lead to a rise in sustainability reporting.

X₄>0, an increase in female membership of remuneration will lead to a rise in sustainability reporting.

X₅>0, a rise in female membership of risk committee will lead to a rise in sustainability reporting.

X₆>0, a rise in leverage will lead to a rise in sustainability reporting.

X₇>0, an increase in firm listing age will lead to a rise in sustainability reporting.

X₈>0, a rise in firm size will lead to a rise in sustainability reporting.

X₉>0, a rise in firm growth will lead to a rise in sustainability reporting.

4 Results and Discussions

This section starts with a descriptive analysis of the variables of interest. A descriptive analysis is a summary of the variables of interest. It shows the number of observations, central mean, standard deviation, minimum mean and maximum mean (see Table 2). Also, the study conducts a

correlation analysis and the results are in Table 3. Furthermore, the study conducts a GMM regression analysis and the results are in Table 4. It is instructive to note that the regression results are subjected to robustness test.

Table 2. *Descriptive Statistics*

Variable	Obs	Mean	Std. Dev.	Min	Max
SR	2,010	.523	.501	0	1
FCEO	2,010	.02	.139	0	1
FACM	2,010	15.713	14.544	0	50
FD	2,010	14.646	10.736	0	60
FRCM	2,010	3.203	8.94	0	33.333
FRICM	2,010	8.072	12.466	0	50
LEV	2,010	86.943	19.254	8.63	254.75
LAGE	2,010	22.693	15.512	2	50
FS	2,010	8.958	.463	8.03	10.77
FG	2,010	27.776	41.099	-65.94	224.98

Source: STATA 15.1 Outputs

As indicated in the results in Table 2, the number of observations for all the variables of the study is 2,010, derived from the product of number of firms (134) and number of years (15). SR averages .523, FCEO averages .02, FACM averages 15.713, FD averages 14.646, FRCM averages 3.203, and FRICM averages 8.072. On the control variables, LEV averages 86.943, LAGE averages 23 years, FS averages 8.958, and FG averages 27.776.

In terms of the volatility of the variables, which is measured by the standard deviation, SR has .501, which is extremely large at 95.79 percent (.501/.523) of the mean. This result is a vindication of the need to carry out further research on sustainability reporting, like this study. In addition, the standard deviation of FCEO is .139, FACM is 14.544, FD is 10.736, FRCM is 8.96, and FRICM is 12.466. On the control variables LEV is 19.254, LAGE is approximately 16 years, FS is .463, and FG is 41.099, another highly volatile variable, which provides a source of concern to managers.

On the minimum mean, SR is 0, FCEO is 0, FACM is 0, FD is 0, FRCM is 0, and FRICM is 0. On the control variables, LEV is 8.63, LAGE is 2 years, FS is 8.03, and FG is -65.94. In terms of maximum mean SR is 1, FCEO is 1, FACM is 50 percent, FD is 60 percent, FRCM is 33.33

percent, and FRICM is 50 percent. On the control variables, LEV is 254.75, LAGE is 50 years, FS is 10.77, and FG is 224.98.

Furthermore, the study conducts a correlation analysis and the results are reported in Table 3 as follows.

Table 3. *Correlation Matrix*

Variables	(1)	(2)	(3)	(4)	(5)	(6)	(7)	(8)	(9)	(10)
(1) SR	1.000									
(2) FCEO	0.135* (0.096)	1.000								
(3) FACM	-0.076 (0.391)	0.187* (0.033)	1.000							
(4) FD	0.389* (0.000)	-0.016 (0.848)	0.205* (0.019)	1.000						
(5) FRCM	0.123 (0.130)	0.081 (0.317)	0.102 (0.248)	0.141 (0.082)	1.000					
(6) FRICM	0.069 (0.395)	0.193* (0.017)	0.029 (0.746)	-0.089 (0.275)	0.032 (0.693)	1.000				
(7) LEV	-0.150* (0.064)	-0.040 (0.628)	0.060 (0.499)	0.018 (0.830)	-0.021 (0.796)	0.015 (0.858)	1.000			
(8) LAGE	0.172* (0.033)	0.180* (0.026)	0.077 (0.385)	0.122 (0.134)	-0.091 (0.264)	0.386* (0.000)	0.102 (0.211)	1.000		
(9) FS	0.414* (0.000)	0.017 (0.837)	-0.086 (0.329)	0.306* (0.000)	-0.236* (0.003)	0.199* (0.014)	-0.224* (0.005)	0.273* (0.001)	1.000	
(10) FG	-0.139 (0.101)	-0.040 (0.634)	-0.173 (0.060)	-0.234* (0.005)	0.048 (0.573)	-0.164 (0.053)	-0.203* (0.016)	-0.274* (0.001)	-0.250* (0.003)	1.000

Source: STATA 15.1 Outputs

From the results in Table 3, it is crystal clear that the bivariate relationship between FCEO and SR is positive and significant at 10 percent. Also, the bivariate relationship between FACM and SR is negative and insignificant. The bivariate relationship between FD and SR is positive and significant at 1 percent. Furthermore, the bivariate relationship between FRCM and SR is positive and insignificant. In the same vein, the bivariate relationship between FRICM and SR is positive and insignificant. On the control variables, the bivariate relationship between LEV and SR is negative and significant at 10 percent. However, in contrast, the bivariate relationship between LAGE and SR is positive and significant at 5 percent. Similarly, the bivariate relationship between FS and SR is positive and significant at 1 percent. Finally, the bivariate relationship between FG and SR is negative and insignificant.

Furthermore, we examine the effect of women directors on SR and the results are reported in Table 4 as follows.

Table 4. GMM Regression Results

Number of parameters = 10

Number of moments = 10

Initial weight matrix: Unadjusted

Number of obs = 2,010

R² = .4558

Prob>Chi² = .000

GMM weight matrix: Robust

	Coef.	Std. Err.	z	P>z	[95% Conf. Interval]
FCEO	.5715365	.1313013	4.35	0.000	.3141907 .8288823
FACM	-.0026023	.0023381	-1.11	0.266	-.0071849 .0019804
FD	.000755	.0034928	0.22	0.829	-.0060907 .0076007
FRCM	.0158654	.003734	4.25	0.000	.0085469 .0231839
FRICM	-.0004076	.0032279	-0.13	0.900	-.0067343 .005919
LEV	-.0036513	.0028874	-1.26	0.206	-.0093106 .002008
LAGE	-.0104519	.0030192	-3.46	0.001	-.0163695 -.0045344
FS	.9622427	.1139344	8.45	0.000	.7389355 1.18555
FG	-.0004948	.0010671	-0.46	0.643	-.0025863 .0015966
/b0	-7.541472	1.091969	-6.91	0.000	-9.681693 -5.401251

Source: STATA 15.1 Outputs

As shown in the results in Table 4, the beta coefficient of FCEO is positive. It reads that for every unit engagement of female CEO, SR rises by 57 percent. This result is also significant, meaning that stakeholders should give special consideration by engaging female CEO. In addition, FACM offers little negative impact on SR. It means that for every unit inclusion of female in audit committee, SR decreases. This result is not significant, implying that stakeholders have not to appreciate the role of audit committee in SR. Furthermore, FD has little positive impact on SR, the impact is also not significant, and suggesting that stakeholders have not come to terms with the role of female director is SR in Nigeria. FRCM has positive and significant effect on SR, though the impact is minimal at 1.586 percent. In contrast, FRICM has negative impact on SR, yet the impact is not significant. However, it offers on every unit inclusion of female on risk committee of firms, a meagre .041 percent reduction in SR. On the control variables, LEV is also negative with .365 percent impact that is not significant on SR. LAGE has a negative, but significant effect on SR, with 1.045 percent impact on SR. FS has positive and significant effect on SR at 96.22 percent, suggesting that for every unit expansion under by the firms under consideration, SR rises. FG offers little negative and insignificant effect on SR at .04948 percent.

These results have both policy and performance improvement implications. They suggests that the engagement of women as CEO as a firm is a determinant of SR, among the 134 listed firms under

consideration in this study. Also, the inclusion of women in the remuneration committee of a firm is, also a determinant of SR in Nigeria. In addition, listing age and firm size are also determinants of SR in Nigeria. Stakeholders should take measures to implement these findings. For example, while the CBN requires banks to appoint a minimum of 30 percent board members as women, the Codes of Corporate Governance from the Financial Reporting Council of Nigeria (2018) is not explicit on the subject. Based on our a priori expectations, the results that are significant are consistent with our expectations, for example, FCEO is positive, FRCM is positive, LAGE is expected to be positive or negative and firm size is similarly expected to be positive or negative with SR. the remaining section focuses on conclusions and recommendations.

Furthermore, the results' R^2 is .4558, which means that the joint effects of the independent variable (women directors) and control variables explain about 45.58 percent of the variations in sustainability reporting. This means that other factors not considered in this study are responsible for the remaining 54.42 percent. Also, the $\text{Prob}>\text{Chi}^2$ is .000, which is significant, that is the model is fit for the study.

5 Conclusions and Recommendations

This paper examines the role of women directors on sustainability reporting of 134 listed firms on the Nigerian Exchange, for 15 years (2008-2022). A multiple regression analysis was used to capture the relationship between female directors and sustainability reporting. The method of analysis is the Generalized Method of Moments. The software used in the analysis is STATA 15.1. The results of descriptive statistics show that SR is volatile, when the mean (.523) is compared with its standard deviation (.501). Also, the results of correlation analysis show that FCEO, FD, LEV, LAGE and FS are significantly correlated with SR. Furthermore, the results of the GMM regression analysis show that FCEO, FRCM, LAGE, and FS have significant effects on SR. The study fails to find similar results for FACM, FD, FRICM, and FG.

This paper offers novel evidence on the relationship between women directors and sustainability reporting. This study's findings may serve policymakers, regulators, investments analysts, investors and academic researchers to get valuable guidance from relevant literature. The firms under study may improve SR by implementing the regulatory framework introduced by the Nigerian Corporate Governance Codes (2018) for effective implementation of the role of women directors in sustainability reporting. The female directors may alleviate principal-agent conflicts

by ensuring that the number of female directors are increased according to the Codes of Conduct. This study contributes to agency theory by considering the role of women directors in ensuring that sustainability reports are published.

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